

Machine Learning Specialization Study notes

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- For multiclass classification, the recommended way to implement softmax regression (Logistic regression) is to set `from_logits=True` in the loss function, and also to define the model's output layer with a 'linear' activation.
- In back propagation and simple calculus, the key when choosing ϵ (epsilon) is that choosing a small value that will keep the result of the loss to increase $K \times \epsilon$ (epsilon), and that means the derivative of the loss equals K .

For example to find the derivative:

$W = 2, j = w^2 = 4$ and when $\epsilon = 0.001, w = 2+0.001, j(w) = 4.004001$, which means the derivative is $= 4$.

- A library for symbolic mathematics, where it possible to find derivatives and integrations is [SymPy](#)

Decision tree:

- A decision tree work by making binary classifications, starting from the root node and going down to the decision nodes, ending with leaf nodes.
- Learning process:
 - o Choose a feature for the root node and another for each decision node and a single feature for each leaf node.

- o The features that get selected on each node, are the ones that maximize purity, or minimize impurity

- The splitting of the nodes stops at the points when a node is all of a single class,
- The impurity of a set of training examples get measured using the entropy.
- The best entropy is 1 which means $H(0.5) = 1$ and that is the best split for the training examples, and the splitting stops when the information gain becomes so small that will not improve the tree as much as cost for adding size to it.
- To calculate the information gain (reduction in entropy) for a node in the tree:

$$\text{Information gain} = H(P_1^{\text{root}}) - (w^{\text{left}} H(P_1^{\text{left}}) + w^{\text{right}} H(P_1^{\text{right}}))$$

Where:

H(): entropy

P(): purity

W: weight

- To build decision trees for more than binary classes, use one-hot encoding
- For continuous features, try different thresholds and split on the threshold that gives the best information gain.
- It is also possible to train regression trees, not only classification trees.
- Using multiple decision trees (ensembling) enable finding the best tree.
- Sampling with replacement: is important when building ensemble random trees, and it is done by replacing the example chosen for building the model with another one, in order to build unique trees each time instead of repeating the same process with the same data each time.

Random forest:

- It is an ensemble of decision trees,

XGBoost:

- Boosted trees get built by focusing the training of a tree on a certain part of the training set that was not well classified in the past tree ensembles.

Decision tree vs. Neural network:

- DTs are for structured data, fast and human interpretable, XGBoost is more computationally expensive

- NNs works for any type of data, slower than DTs, works with transfer learning and it is easier to ensemble many models

Anomaly detection:

- The anomaly detection process is unsupervised, and to evaluate a model we can use the following parameters:
 - o Confusion matrix
 - o Precision/recall
 - o F1-score
- Anomaly detection using:
 - o Unsupervised learning: choose it when:
 - A very small (or no) number of positive examples and large number of negatives
 - Get used when the anomalies are various and may not be repeated at inference time. (financial fraud)
 - o Supervised learning:
 - Could use it for skewed datasets and balanced ones.
 - Get used when the anomalies that get detected at inference are the same as the ones the model was trained on. (email spam)
- When choosing features for anomaly detection we look for gaussian distributed features, or transform the non-gaussian to its log to become that.

Collaborative filtering: recommends items to you based on ratings of users who gave similar ratings as you. (about comparing to the other users)

- For recommenders the loss function used is the square error loss and could be regularized. And the model used is linear regression. And the features of the movies might be the genre of them.
- If we don't have the features and we want to derive it from the information we have and regularize for the features not weights
- So in the general case the parameters are the weights, the biases and the features, and when optimizing all three of them need to be updated.
- In some applications it is okay to work with binary labels and for that could use logistic regression. And in this case use the cross entropy cost function.
- Mean normalization can solve the adding a new user problem by assigning the mean of the existing users as a value to the new unknown user ratings. And the

equation used for the mean is simply subtracting the mean for the movie (for example) from the rating.

Content-based filtering: recommends items to you based on features of user and item to find good match. (about comparing to the user past experience)

- There is no bias to count for in this type of filtering.
- The user and item networks can be equal or different sizes but the final layers must be equal.

Principle component analysis:

- Commonly used for visualization
- It is about finding a new axis and coordinates, that will allow using fewer numbers to capture the full information about the object. (feature reduction)
- The PCA is the line where the points projection have the smallest distance from as a sum of distances.
- The second principal component is perpendicular to the first and the third is perpendicular to both of them.
- PCA is different from linear regression, and as follows:
 - Linear regression: try to minimize the distance on the y-axis (vertical projection). And linear regression is always cross the y-axis.
 - PCA: try to minimize the projection of the data on the fitted line (2D projection). It could fit or be parallel to the y-axis.
- Building a PCA model happens by:
 - Feature scaling
 - Fit the data to obtain new axes
 - Optionally examine how much variance is explained by each axis
 - Transform the data onto the new axes.
- PCA is used for:
 - Visualization.
 - Data compression.
 - Speeding up training.

Reinforcement learning:

- Some terminology:

- States, which could mean positions of the robot or postures.
 - Actions means the movements and steps taken.
 - Rewards are points get given to the robot when they take the correct action and get to the correct state.
 - Return: is the sum of all the rewards for the robots on the path multiplied by the discount factor.
 - Policy (π): is the function that tells you which action to take in a certain state.
 - Markov decision process (MDP): where Markov refers to the fact that the future depends only on the current state and has nothing to do with the prior states
 - State-action value function: or the Q function which maximize the reward for the state and the action to be taken.
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- The Bellman equation: it is the function for the q-learning and defined as:
 $Q(s,a) = R(s) + \gamma \max_{a'} Q(s', a')$ and it breaks down into the following:
 $Q(s,a) = R_1 + \gamma R_2 + \gamma^2 R_3 + \gamma^3 R_4 \dots$
 This sequence of terms is as long as the distance to be traveled to get to the terminal state.
 - The stochastic reinforcement learning (Markov decision process): in this case the goal is to choose the policy that will tell us which action to take to maximize the expected return. And it changes the Bellman equation by considering the expected maximum of the q-equation instead of taking the equation directly.
 - For a continuous state space, the state get represented in many numbers such as the coordinates and the orientation.
 - In deep reinforcement learning we could feed the model a set of states and actions and the network will compute Q for the state and action given. Then at inference you will give it a state and list of possible actions and when it computes Qs for them you pick the action with the highest Q value to apply it.
 - To train a neural network on reinforcement learning we create a dataset based on Bellman equation and that is by inputting states and actions and finding their Q-values then train the network just like supervised learning. And the result is called a DQN or deep Q network.

- To pick actions while you are still learning use the epsilon-greedy policy. And how exactly to do that is by choosing one of the following options:
 - Option1: pick the action a that maximizes $Q(s,a)$
 - Option2: with probability 0.95 choose the action a that maximizes $Q(s,a)$ (greedy action / exploitation), and with probability 0.05 pick an action a randomly. (exploration)
- Using mini-batches would improve the speed of training of the RL network.